

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

SMART MOBILITY AND MICRO-MOBILITY: A
NEW PERSPECTIVE OF PUBLIC AND
INDIVIDUAL TRANSPORT IN SMART CITIES
Author: Juliana Miranda Martins

POLICY STATEMENT

This article is based on the report *17° Rapporto sulla mobilità degli Italiani* and presents a series of initiatives put into practice in the main European capitals and cities in the context of public policies for smart mobility. If, on the one hand, the report reveals what the empirical observation already found: the COVID-19 Pandemic profoundly influenced the mobility of large urban centers, encouraging an already growing trend of alternative mobility, on the other hand, it presents an Italian and European photograph of evolution of urban transport, the typologies of alternative electric transport (AETs) and the response in terms of public policies of the main European cities. These new forms of mobility demonstrate the desire and awareness of citizens who want to move in a smarter way, less impacting on the environment and social life, as well as the social impacts generated by the pandemic.

BACKGROUND

Smart mobility is the current definition for the traffic of alternative individual, double, family or group transports powered by electricity or zero gas emissions. In this category are also cars, bicycles and scooters (electric or not). Inside *Smart mobility* there is the *micro-mobility*, a term used to define the traffic of individual alternative electric transport (or not, in the case of pedestrians on foot).

Micro-mobility and light mobility are the terms used both by urban planners and in the computer world, coined by the French authors Cyprien Richer and Mathieu Rabaud. According to their definition, personal mobility devices and electrical assistance devices are classified according to their empty weight and portability: 1) empty mass (less than 15 kg, from 15 to 40 and more than 40 kg); 2) motorization and speed (without motor therefore on foot and with electric assistance only, up to 25 km / h speed, from 25 to 45 km / h) [p.121]. In this category are, for example, electric scooters, segway (single skates with handlebars), monowheel, balance bike or pedalless electric bicycle (e-pedelec), hoverboard (also with handlebars).

The main European capitals have developed important urban initiatives and action plans, of which we can highlight: Amsterdam, which reduced the speed limit to 30km/h and closed roads in the vicinity of schools and neighborhood areas; The London's Mayor's Streetspace Plan with the project to widen the sidewalks and increase the cyclo-pedestrian network; Berlin carried out a pilot project to increase the structure of cities and adapt them with electricity poles for these devices in parks; Paris with the "*Plan Velo*" project that foresees the external lane in the streets and avenues and the closing of streets in the neighborhoods; Barcelona put into practice the project "sustainable mobility in a new public space", with 97 new biking sharing stations in the neighborhoods; Portugal encourages citizens to walk in the streets with the project "The street is yours", and many others all born during the year 2020. The main Italian cities such as Rome (cycle project "transitory"), Turin (plan for mobility), Milan (Open Roads project), Naples (Naples advances), Bologna (*Bicipolitana*) followed the European trend.

The data from the Italian cyclist industry (second place in production and first in bicycle exports at the European level) confirms the phenomenon of a total growth of about 60% (normal bicycle and e-bike) in relation to the years before the pandemic. There has also been a great growth at the European level in the manufacture, circulation, sale and export of AETs type micro-mobility.

FINDINGS

Several reasons have contributed to increase the demand for Alternative Electric Transports (AETs) especially in the post-pandemic period:

1. Technological innovations: The e-bikes and e-scooters reduced the periphery-center exposure times enabling the use of these transports not only for leisure or sport, but also for daily traffic activity as well as for working and studying. The increase in the autonomy of the AETs' batteries enables the user to use it systematically for more significant distances and, finally, the portability of these means (foldable e-bikes and scooters, small-sized one, two or three-wheel AETs, etc.), which expanded the possibility of connection with traditional public transport (with their own parking at railway stations or which allow the user to take their individual transport with them).
2. Economy for users and public administration: AETs are economical for the cost of fuel as they can be electrically charged. The acquisition, maintenance and parking costs of AETs are substantially lower than those of an ordinary car. The agility and short times related to its intrinsically "smart" characteristic represent savings in time, space, money and in the medium and long time, savings in road maintenance for cities.
3. Concern for the environment and the emission of harmful gases in big cities: The growth of social awareness about the problems related to global warming has stimulated fewer polluting choices among European citizens. The issue still deserves reflection regarding the demolition of lithium batteries, but it is a common point that the advantages are greater than the disadvantages. Other important impact reductions can be mentioned, for example, the reduction of noise pollution from traditional public transport, the absence and the problem of spaces destined for parking lots, the process of waterproofing the ground as a result of it and its high cost to the taxpayers. Recently, the social impact of the post pandemic era: fear of crowding in subways and buses has led people to opt for individual means of exposure.
4. The search for physical and mental wellness, healthy habits and the practice of physical exercises: Even before the pandemic, this trend was observed among Europeans and it intensified during and after it. The pandemic gave the decisive impetus. Despite the frenzy of post-modern society, the idea of joining regular physical exercises to public transport in the same delta time was an increasingly diffused notion from the mass use of the normal bicycle and intensified with the advent of e-bike pedaling assisted.
5. Finally, the attraction exerted by the AETs, their playful, irreverent, technological form, but at the same time efficient and safe (medium speed controlled and reduced compared to traditional means of transport) has a prognosis of great acceptance in the coming years. Some cities saw the vanguardism of such transport as an opportunity to redefine the viability and motivate their fellow citizens to use AETs and at the same time expand the network of bicycle paths, revitalize spaces related to cultural heritage and public parks, in short, add value to public transport, providing smart solutions for the new user and their new experience of moving with quality in their own city.

CONCLUSIONS

To achieve the goals set by the Climate Summit in New York 2019, in which 66 countries, 102 cities and 93 multinationals accepted the commitment of zero emission of toxic gases by the year 2050, a substantial change in lifestyle is necessary. In the post-modern era we are witnessing a scenario in which States do not take action until there is an emergency or a great social demand for change. A consequence of the COVID-19 crisis is an awareness that the lifestyle inherited from the 20th century is destroying the planet and making people sick. The use of AETs is only a first step towards reaching the zero-emission target, but it is certainly a decisive step towards breaking the imaginary barrier (implicit in minds for generations) that it is impossible to replace fossil fuels.

SUGGESTIONS

The following are suggestions to improve, develop and expand the smart mobility system to large cities around the world:

- In the mobility plans of the mentioned cities, there is a predominant concern of the public administration in increasing and improving the network of cycle paths. However, it is necessary to take into account the improvement of public institutions and the private sector to provide infrastructure for the AETs and achieve the objective set in several of these projects: for example, the public sector, starting with schools and companies, invest and provide parking spaces for these transports.
- The public transport system must adapt to the connection with micro-mobility: Make the portability of AETs viable, easy and free of charge (with or without electrical assistance): So that people can take the train, bus or transport your own device to eliminate a second mode of transport. The public administration must also invest in the electricity of the bus fleet.
- Increase of state incentives for purchases and electric energy for AETs: Public economic incentives are a reality in several European countries, for example in Italy, such as the auto electric bonus (40% discount on the purchase of an electric car), Bicycle Bonus (19% discount on the purchase of AETs) and the cargo-bike bonus for self-employed workers who make delivery (30% discount of state reimbursement for electricity expenses). In addition, the "Eco bonus incentive": in the demolition of a car, the user can obtain up to 40% of the electric car's value.
- Use of international cooperation (also at the local level) for the transfer of technology to developing countries in order to make economically viable prototypes for these countries. Encouragement of all types of international collaboration.
- Education and training for a sustainable traffic culture, reinforcing the idea of smart mobility in collective and micro-mobility for individual exposure, promoting sustainability and giving the user the responsibility to reach the common goal regarding zero emission of toxic gases by 2050.

REFERENCES

17° *Rapporto sulla mobilità degli Italiani*. Tra la gestione del presente e strategie per il futuro, ISFORT Istituto Superiore di Formazione e ricerca per i trasporti, Roma, 2020

<https://www.isfort.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/RapportoMobilita2020.pdf> (accessed 10/06/2021).

Marques da Silva, José Carlos,. *Sistema de mobilidade elétrica de duas rodas de elevada eficiência e performance*, Tese de Mestrado, Instituto Politécnico de Viseu, Escola Superior de Tecnologia e Gestão de Viseu, Viseu, 2013 <https://repositorio.ipv.pt/handle/10400.19/2009> (accessed 25/05/2021).

Plan National Velo. Ministre des Transports et le groupe de travail. Paris, Janvier, 2012.

http://www.greencode.fr/wp-content/uploads/2012/02/Plan-National-V%C3%A9lo_26.01.2012.pdf (accessed 11/07/2021).